

VOICE, CONTEXT, LANGUAGE - THE DEVELOPMENT OF HUNGARIAN MUSIC FROM DANCE TO MUSIC: A STUDY OF HUNGARIAN MUSIC FOCUSING ON "CHARDASHI"

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Abstract

Chardash (Hungarian: Csárdás, Czárdás, pronounced char'dash, derived from csárda, meaning inn), also known as Chardash, Chardash, Chardash, Chardash, Chardash, Chardash, Chardash, is a Hungarian folk dance. Originating from the Mazars and Gypsies. Chardash originated from verbunkos in the 18th century and was originally a dance music used by Hungarian army conscripts. Its characteristic is the variation of rhythm: slow and fast. Start with a slow pace (lassú) and end with a fast pace (friss). There are also other types of rhythm changes, called ritka csárdás, sürű csárdás, szökő csárdás. The music has a beat of 2/4 or 4/4. Dancers include both men and women. The female dancer wore a traditional wide skirt, usually a red one. When a female dancer rotates, the wide skirt will form a unique shape. Classical music composers often incorporate the Chardasian style into their works, including writers such as Liszt, Brahms, John Strauss, Tchaikovsky, and others. This article will introduce Hungarian music research represented by this art form and musical works.

Keywords: Chardashi, dance, musical works, development history.

1. Tracing the Origin of Hungarian Music from the Perspective of Voice

Hungary has made significant contributions to the world of folk music, including popular and classical music. Hungarian folk music is also a significant pillar and symbol of Hungarian self-identity, and continues to play a crucial role in neighboring regions such as Romania, Slovakia, southern Poland, especially the Romanian settlements in southern Slovakia and Transylvania, as it is also the home of many Hungarians. In addition, it also has a considerable degree of influence in the Soboroch Sotmar Belag region, as well as in the southwestern Transdanubia region adjacent to Croatia. The Busójárás Carnival, held annually in the city of Mohács, is a major event in the Hungarian folk music industry today. In the past, it was represented by the historic and internationally renowned Bogyszóló orchestra.

Classical music in Hungary has long been like the music experiment that has been circulating on the land of Hungary for a long time, and the widespread dissemination of its folk music, were used to create their own deep and self-awareness music culture. Although the Hungarian upper class had close connections with other European countries for a long time, which allowed music concepts from all over Europe to flow into Hungary, rural farmers were also able to preserve and continue their own traditions. Therefore, in the late 19th century, Hungary Only composers can draw nutrients from rural peasant music and create a unique classical music style that is different from the past in Hungary. For example, Bartok Bela and Gao Dayi, the two most famous Hungarian composers, are known for using folk elements in their personal works. Bartok collected folk songs from the entire Eastern European region (including Romania and Slovakia), while Gao Dayi focused on finding unique and distinct parts of Hungarian music. During the communist rule of Hungary in 1944, the government established a song review committee. At that time, he advocated for the purification of consciousness and investigated popular music that he believed had the

potential to incite the public. However, from this moment on, Hungary's music industry gradually recovered, cultivating many successful musicians in various fields of music - jazz, such as trumpet player Rudolf Tosiz, pianist and composer Carlo Binder, who combined Hungarian folk songs with modern music. In addition, there are Ferenc Saibu and Marta Sebastian. The three important groups of Hungarian rock music - Illés, Metró, and Omega - are still popular among the public, especially Omega, which is very popular in Hungary and Germany. Old underground groups such as Sziámi and Európa Kiadó were still popular in the 1980s.

Different from other places in Europe, Hungarians and Magyars originated from the 5th to 8th century, when the Finnish Ugric language group and the people of East Türkiye settled here and gradually blended, which is the origin of Hungarian traditional music and most of the music differences in Europe. According to Simon Broughton's research, the songs identified by Gao Dayi are similar to the Russian Malian language family - "clearly dating back 2500 years ago. Bruno Nettl, a music researcher in cultural anthropology, pointed out that traditional Hungarian music has high similarities in form and elements with Mongolian and Native American music. [8]. Bence Szabolcsi's research pointed out that "although it is impossible to clearly identify the relevant objects or specific ethnic language families, Finn Uk and Mongolian Türkiye elements are also among them." Even so, Szabolcsi still believes that Hungarian traditional music is closely related to Malian, Kalmyk, Chinese (Ostyak), Chinese music in the northwest, Tartar, Vogul, Türkiye music, Bashkirian, Mongolian music and Chuvash music. He believes that these all prove that "previous exchanges and memories with Asia have fallen asleep and flowed deep in Hungarian folk music, which is a part of the Western world's continuous connection with the ancient East in terms of musical form

According to Broughton, traditional Hungarian music, like 'Hungarian', has a high degree of specificity, with stress often located on the first syllable, resulting

in a strongly accented Dactyl rhythm in the music. Nettl identified two "key qualities" of Hungarian folk music: "including the use of pentatonic scales (composed of major second and minor third, or gapped scales), as well as the main axis of the song created by repeated variations of some melodies." These variations "typically rise and fall in the Perfect fifth," creating a harmonious pan tone interval. There are indications that the important feature of this pentatonic scale may be influenced by Chinese music. According to Szabolcsi research, The "certain melodies, rhythms and decorative sounds" associated with these Hungarian tonal variations can clearly show the characteristics of Turks moving from east to west in Eurasia. The music of neighboring countries that are obviously affected by this, such as Slovakia, will also be accompanied by the second or third interval. The music of the Czech Republic, Hungary and other Finno languages also has the characteristics of using the two musical forms of "A-B-B-A". The more well-known usage of Hungarian personal music is the transformation of A A 'A' A, where the segment of B is transformed from the segment of A in the pentatonic (ascending or descending)

2. A Contextual Perspective on Hungarian Music and "Chardash"

The earliest recorded surviving Hungarian music is the Gregorian Chant, which was introduced in the 11th century. The earliest recorded instruments can be traced back to the whistle in 1222, the kobzos in 1326, the military horn in 1355, the violin in 1358, the bagpipe in 1402, the flute in 1427, and the trumpet in 1428. Later, the organ played an important role in music performance. In 1508, N á dor Codex used the Gregorian hymn as the melody blueprint for the first time, adding the Hungarian's own musical style.

In the 16th century, Chuanxifania (a region never occupied by Turks in the northeast of Hungary) rose to become the center of Hungarian music creation, and Krakow published Hungarian music works for the first time. Hungarian performance music was quite well-known in Europe at that time, for example, flute and composer B á lint Bakfark was a renowned master performer. His composition has developed a completely new style, emphasizing the coordination between flute and vocals. Flute player Neusiedler brothers created many important early works, and their works on constructing music theory are included in Epithoma utriusque musices [15].

In the 17th century, Hungary was divided into three parts: one was controlled by the Turks, the other was ruled by Habsburg, and the other was Chuanxifania. Songs that have been passed down since ancient times have gradually lost their mass market and have been replaced by poetry (palace musicians have replaced bards). They play trumpets, whistles, chimbals, violins, or bagpipes, and many palaces or royal families have their own large-scale performance groups. The musicians are all from Germany, Poland, France, or Italy. The musicians of Prince G á bor Bethlen of Transylvania even included guitarists from Spain, but there was not much information on the music of this period that has been passed down.

In the mid-19th century, some of the college students in the S á rospatak and Sz é kelyudvarhely regions were middle to lower class aristocrats who originally came from rural areas and brought the music style of their region. The choir forms circulating in these universities have adopted more polyphonic forms, and students' songbooks have shown the gradually widespread popularity of many similar songs. However, they still use the original song as a notation, so there is no extended form of song inclusion in it. Until Á d á m P á l ó czi Horv á th published Ö t ö df é lsz á z É nekek in 1853, these songs showed that in the mid to late 18th century, the style of traditional Hungarian songs gradually disappeared, and musicians began to seek creative inspiration by moving closer to Western music. In the 18th century, Verbankos (Soldier Music, Verbankos) also gradually emerged. This type of music, originally used for military conscription, was similar to most Hungarian music at the time, where melody was more important than lyrics, even though this trait has changed in recent years due to the popularity of Verbankos. Chardas (Hungarian: Cs á rd á s, Cz á rd á s; English: Czardas) is Vittorio Monti's most famous piece. Rhapsody based on a famous Hungarian song written by Chaldash in 1904. The song was originally composed for the violin, mandolin, and piano. Today, it is mostly used as a violin piece, and can also be used as a piano solo, saxophone solo, accordion, or adapted into orchestral music or bassoon solo.

3. A Study of Hungarian Music in Different Language Backgrounds

Among classical music around the world, the most significant Hungarian musician is Liszt [37], a master of Hungarian rhapsodies and preludes, and a highly respected pianist and composer of the 19th century. The era of Liszt's existence was also the time when modern Hungarian classical music, seeking its own essence, took shape. In addition to Liszt, the Italian and French style operas produced by the same period's Ferenc Akel were also paired with Hungarian lines. In addition, the master of German classical style, Mihaly Mosonyi, paved the way for future music development, and their impact was unparalleled by successors. This is not only because of their personal talent, but also because they strive to integrate the essence of Loma music into their works, and passionately unleash tradition to the fullest. Hungary has also nurtured many outstanding musicians, such as composer Carl Godmark, who created the Rustic Wedding Symphony, composer and pianist Erno Dohnani, and piano composer Stephen Heller. Many violinists from Hungary are internationally renowned, especially Yao Axing Joseph and Jen ő Hubay, Edward Remenyi, and Leopold Orr. The conductors born in Hungary include Antal Dor á ti, Eugene Omandi, Fritz Lena, and George Sel.

The origin of Hungarian opera was the rise of opera introduced from abroad in the late 18th century. At that time, many regions such as Pozsony, Kismarton, Sibiu, and Budapest held concerts, and were mostly influenced by Germanic or Italian opera. The development of Hungarian opera originated from the adaptation of drama schools and Germanic opera, which included Pauline School located in S á toralja ú

jhely, Calvinist School located in Csurgó, and Piarist School located in Budapest. The first musical attempt was the "Prince Pikkó and Jutka Perzsi" produced by Gáspár Pacha and József Chudy in Bratislava in late 1793, which was also widely recognized as the first Hungarian opera. This drama is the translation of "Prinz Schnudi und Prinzessin Evakathel" created by freelance translator Philipp Hafner. The opera of this period still had a strong comedic style originating from the Zauberpösse form in Vienna, which lasted until the 19th century. But even if foreign opera forms were adopted, the "poetry, lyrics, and protagonists" in the story were still based on verbunkos and became a symbol of Hungary's national state at this time. In the mid-19th century, Ferenc Erkel adopted models from France and Italy to create the first opera pronounced in Hungarian.

The development of Hungarian music in the late 19th century was dominated by German classical music, but this situation changed by 1905. At this time, Endre Ady began publishing poetry collections, composer Bartok Bella also published his first works, and Gao Dayi also began collecting folk songs. Bartok and Gao Dayi are both excellent composers, and their music has a distinctive Hungarian style. Gao Dayi is particularly focused on Hungarian folk music, while Bartok is interested in various types of folk music. Therefore, he collects information on traditional folk songs in Eastern European countries (especially Hungary) and applies them to his music creation. Compared to previous composers who attempted to explore the local culture of Hungary, Gao Dayi and Bartok did not combine Loma with Hungarian national music. Instead, they provided a detailed classification of the later development forms of the two, and their musical achievements were seen as an important watershed that influenced "Hungarian tradition" and "future domestic composers".

In the early 20th century, Bartok and Gao Dayi were the most influential representatives - especially during the revival of traditional choral folk songs by Gao Dayi in 1947. However, this trend was forced to cease in the 1950s, when communism, advocated by the state, was superior to everything else. At that time, "faith and consciousness became the benchmark for composers when creating music, and shameful adjectives such as 'formalistic' and 'cosmopolitan' became popular at that time. Classical arias, arias, or sonatas became the main definition of formal Hungarian music. They eliminated the joyful and optimistic atmosphere that could lead to biased ideas in Gao Dayi's works, resulting in a dull and uninteresting outcome that lost public support. The well-known composers at the time were Endre Szervánszky and Lajos Bárdos.

Starting around 1955, a new generation of composers inspired by Bartok gradually emerged, adding new elements to Hungarian music. Composers of this era include Ferenc Szabó, Endre Szervánszky, Pál Kadosa, Ferenc Farkas, and György Ránki. In addition to returning to the techniques of Hungarian music, they also adopted avant-garde and modern elements from Western classical music introduced at the time.

Conclusion

Since the birth of the Hungarian nation, music has been an important component of its culture. Although the practice of artistic music is retained within a limited circle, this does not prevent it from producing important musicians. At the end of the 18th century, verbunkos, a "wedding dance", emerged and spread to various parts of the world through Hungarian composers in the 19th century, along with Franz Liszt, Mihai Mosoni, and Ferenc Erkel, helping the country create an identity of learned music. The friendship between Bella Bartok and Zoltan Kodály later became the source of Hungarian music development in the 20th century. They encountered a common desire to rediscover the foundation of their national style, on which their predecessors developed Hungarian music. These two individuals studied the oral traditions of the Hungarian peasant class in order to extract all the rich artistic and scientific content from them. This is not like the "folklore" they are accused of, but rather a desire to integrate Hungarian music into their creations like European culture.

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